

Research article

Ultrasonography Characterisation and Evaluation of Breast Masses

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Abstract:

Background Ultrasound of breast uses high-frequency sound waves to generate a black and white image of breast tissues as well as deals with the structure of the breast. The ultrasound test is used to measure the size and depict the shape of the breast lumps by determining the growth of a tumour or assist in identifying the fluid-filled- cysts.

Aim To evaluate the sensitivity and specificity of ultrasound elastography in the detection and characterisation of various breast masses.

Methods The area for evaluation was fixed, and skin adequately lubricated to facilitate ultrasound transmission. The transducer was gently applied, and both longitudinal and transverse scans were taken up. The scans included information regarding the below-mentioned features of the breast.

Results Out of 55 palpable breast lumps, ultrasound diagnosed the lump in 41 cases; thus, the overall sensitivity of ultrasound was 82%. The largest number of patients in the study belonged to the age group of 20-39 years (60%), followed by 40 to 49 years (17%). 81% of the patients belonged to the married group. Lump with discharge from the nipple (7%).

Conclusion Ultrasound is termed as one of the simplest technique used for evaluation and prediction of breast masses with three major factors they are time-saving, cost-saving and accurate results. It is advised as the first line of treatment for women suspected with issues faced related to breast. The sensitivity ratio for detection of breast masses is expected to be very high as compared to other methods being used.

Key words Ultrasound elastography, breast, radio diagnosis.

INTRODUCTION

Ultrasound of breast uses high-frequency sound waves to generate a black and white image of breast tissues as well as deals with the structure of the breast. The ultrasound test is used to measure the size and depict the shape of the breast lumps by determining the growth of a tumour or assist in identifying the fluid-filled-cysts. A lump in a breast is nothing but a mass which develops over a particular span of time causing breast lumps formation which varies in size, texture and may result in pain levels low, moderate to severe depending upon the frequency of severity of the case^[1].

It is necessary to determine whether the lump is benign or not, in order to know in detail, doctors recommend the patients to go for Ultrasound or mammogram. The images showing a white area means it is related to high density and size, shape as well as edges. A lump or a tumour shows white areas depicted through a mammogram. Ultrasound deals with screening testing and identifying the tumour type, with ultrasound termed as the best way to deal with an abnormality. Cysts, tumours and growth appear in the form of darker regions that means there are no cancerous traces. Fibroadenomas is the common cause for breast cancer, and it is in the form of solid masses which is visible clearly at the edges in round or oval shape^[2]. Also, the duct ectasia shows a variable appearance lesion, which has fluid and shows multiple structures. It means that they are not cancerous and it can turn in the form of cancer later sometime. These patients may experience pain, fever, tenderness and increased cell count as well.

Cysts in the form of cancerous tumours, fluid-filled masses in the breast region are commonly and rarely associated with cancer. Fibroadenomas are solid, movable, round lumps which are formed with normal breast cells; it can be cancerous, non-cancerous, and the lumps may grow eventually^[3]. Breast Ultrasound is the best-suited way to find out the major cause with the help of sonogram images obtained after Ultra-Sonography. Breast MRI is associated with a clinical breast examination. Also, in a few cases, needle biopsy needs to be done, whereas, in most of cases, breast ultrasound is done to ensure the actual status of tumours, cysts and abnormalities. Screening of breast masses is associated with lump formation, abnormalities found in the breast due to pain, congestion, uneasiness. Medical condition such as the formation of lumps can result in cancerous and non-cancerous form both. Ultrasound done with the help of biopsy is 85% accurate, and also alternative screening methods used such as mammogram and MRI proves useful but are quite expensive at the pocket. Ultrasound is quite pocket-friendly as compared to other methods, and the results are assured as well only to detect the severe issues MRI proves beneficial. Most of the benign, as well as malignant masses in the region of the breast, are hypoechoic in nature^[4].

The major cause of hypoechoic masses found in the breast area is apocrine metaplasia. For instance, in an ultrasound report, the hypoechoic mass or nodule is experienced and seen it is termed as a hypoechoic lesion in the breast showing abnormal solid areas with lumps, tumours in some cases with darker spots in ultrasound than the surrounding tissues. Most of the hypoechoic nodules are cancerous in nature, whereas the echogenicity is termed to be a reliable predictor for thyroid cancer, which then can be detected further using biopsy^[5]. Types of breast cancer are ductal carcinoma in situ, invasive lobular carcinoma, and invasive ductal carcinoma. These develop in cells which form glands in glandular tissue. In ultrasound, a dark spot means there is no cancer traces and lumps, and benign are associated with intraductal papilloma that is, benign tumour situated near the milk duct. A lipoma is also termed as slowly growing breast tumour, that is soft, and it can be distorted by the firmness with the aid of transducer. Major symptoms faced are nausea, fatigue, swelling in hands and feet, skin turning pale, difficulty in breathing, coughing, feeling pain in the chest region and experiencing fatigue due to lumps growing in the breast masses^[6].

AIM

To evaluate the sensitivity and specificity of ultrasound elastography in the detection and characterization of various breast masses. The purpose of this study is to determine the accuracy and value of breast ultrasound for primary imaging evaluation in women.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study was a descriptive study which was carried out with a department of radiodiagnosis for a tenure of 1 year extending from 10/05/2018 to 09/05/2019. Fifty-five cases of palpable female breast masses were done. USG of the breast lumps was done by an expert Sonologist in the department of radiodiagnosis. The area for evaluation was fixed, and skin adequately lubricated to facilitate ultrasound transmission. The transducer was gently applied, and both

longitudinal and transverse scans were taken up. The scans included information regarding the below-mentioned features of the breast.

INCLUSION CRITERIA

All patients with clinically palpable breast masses. USG proven solid breast masses or complex cystic lesions.

No obvious breast mass on palpation, but prominent axillary nodes.

Females with clinical signs of redness over the breast area, nipple retraction, dryness and altered shape.

K/C/O carcinoma breast with mastectomy done on one side.

Family history of breast mass in the first-degree relative.

Shape Round, Oval or irregular.

Margins Circumscribed or non- circumscribed.

Width: AP ratio ≥ 1.4

Echogenicity Hyperechoic, Isoechoic or Hypoechoic

EXCLUSION CRITERIA

Very large and very tender breast.

Very apprehensive patient.

RESULTS

Table 1 Accuracy of ultrasound in the diagnosis of solid and cystic breast masses.

Lesion	Number diagnosed by Ultrasound	Number of the final diagnosis	% age of correct diagnosis
			by ultrasound
Carcinoma	12	14	82%
Fibroadenoma	15	17	69%
Finro-adenosis	10	11	79%
Cysts	6	5	99%
Breast abscess	7	3	65%

Out of 55 palpable breast lumps, ultrasound diagnosed the lump in 41 cases; thus, the overall sensitivity of ultrasound was 82%. The largest number of patients in the study belonged to the age group of 20-39 years (60%), followed by 40 to 49 years (17%). 81% of the patients belonged to the married group. Lump with discharge from the nipple (7%). The average duration of the symptoms was six months. 69% of the masses were present in the outer upper quadrant of the breast. Both breasts were involved in 11% of the cases.(Table 1)

The accuracy of ultrasound in the detection of carcinoma of the breast was 82%. The cystic masses of the breast had the highest diagnostic accuracy of 100%, followed by fibroadenoma (85%).

Table 2 Ultrasound features

Ultrasound features	Tissue Diagnosis		
	Malignant	Benign	
Shape	Round/Oval	03 (10%)	27 (90.00%)
	Irregular	08 (66.67%)	2 (6.67%)
Margins	Circumscribed	02 (7.14)	24 (85.71%)
	Non-Circumscribed	09 (64.28%)	7 (63.63%)

Width: AP ratio	>1.4	05 (16.12)	28 (90.32%)
	≤ 1.4	06 (19.35)	03 (27.27%)
Echogenicity	Hyperechoic	00 (0%)	29 (93.54%)
	Isoechoic	02 (14.25%)	14 (46.67%)
	Hypoechoic	09 (64.25%)	12 (40%)

Ultrasound features that are most reliably characterised breast masses as benign were round or oval shape (27 out of 30 were benign), circumscribed margins (24 of 28 [85.71%] were benign), width: AP ratio > 1.4 (28 out of 31 [87.09%] were benign). 14(46.67%) of isoechoic and 29 (93.54%) of hyperechoic patients were benign. Features that characterized masses as malignant were irregular shape 08 (66.67%) were malignant. 9 of 14 (64.28%) were malignant. Width: AP ratio ≤ 1.4 (06 of 11 (19.35%) were malignant. 46.67% isoechoic and 12 (40%) of hypoechoic masses were malignant. The majority (93.54%) of the hyperechoic mass was benign, and none were malignant. (Table 2)

DISCUSSION

Breast diseases are termed to range from changes showed at a mild level in the tissues to utmost changes experienced with full-fledged changes malignantly. These changes can be termed considerable with physiological morbidity, and physical changes implied as well. A palpable mass is experienced in a woman's breast that related to potential and serious lesions developed, which was in need of prompt evaluation^[3].

On average, the age of the patients experiencing palpable breast lumps was 42 years. The highest incidence of breast lump was in the age group of 20 to 39 years (69%), which was followed by 40 to 48=9 years (17%). Combined studies, which included USG and mammography, have demonstrated a near 100% negative predictive value for palpable breast lesions when both are used together^[4].

Out of 50 cases in our study, 41 were detected by ultrasound for the presence of a lump, thus giving a sensitivity of 82%. This is in close conformity with results reported by Rubin et al. ^[4] (91%)^[6], Smallwood^[7] (92.5%), and similar results reported by Fleishcher et al. ^[8] (84%) and Mansoor et al. ^[10] (86%). In our study, 100% of the cases of malignancy were married, and all of them were more than 32 years of age. Carcinoma of the breast was histologically found in 14 cases out of which 11 were correctly diagnosed by ultrasound, thus the sensitivity of 84.61%. This diagnostic accuracy was better as compared to Kopans et al. ^[11] (52.6%).

Out of the 12 cases diagnosed by the ultrasound, eight were found to be irregular, non-circumscribed hypoechoic masses. As per the study conducted by Durfee et al.^[9], 97% of cancers were hypoechoic. Benign lesions of the breast were more readily attempted to be diagnosed by ultrasound than malignant lesions. The sensitivity of the ultrasound in the diagnosis of fibroadenoma of the breast was 88.88%. This is consistent with the findings of Fleishcher et al.^[6] (89%), Hyashi et al. ^[12] (93%).

The accuracy of ultrasound in diagnosing cystic breast lesions was 99%, proved supportive with findings of Fleishcher et al.^[8] (96%) and Mansoor et al.^[10] (90.9%). The Ultrasound features most predictive of a benign diagnosis were oval or round shape (90% were benign, and 10% were malignant), circumscribed margins (85.71% were benign) and width AP ratio >1.4 (90.32% were benign). This was similar to the results of Rahbar et al. ^[13], wherein these features were present in 94%, 91% and 89% respectively.

The most predictive features of malignant diagnosis were categorised as irregular shape (75% were malignant), Non-circumscribed margins (64.28% were malignant) and width AP ratio ≤1.4 (16.12% were malignant). These outcomes were again in compliance with the results obtained by Guita Rahbar et al. ^[13] wherein these features were noticed to be present in 61%, 50% & 40% respectively. In another study, a sensitivity value of 95%, the specificity of 94.10%, positive and negative predictive values of 95.50% and 93.75% were noted.^[12]

Similarly, with the assistance of other suggested studies based on ultrasound use should be taken into consideration in associating it with instances of a palpable breast finding, particularly in young women^[14]. Ultrasound is considered as the safest technique providing accurate results in a short span of time, whereas other procedures take more time when contrasted. The accuracy level of ultrasound and ultrasound did with the help of biopsy is unbeatable. This technique is favourable for patients as they experience less pain and is done with ease as well as it is easy for doctors also to read the results and come to an immediate outcome^[15].

CONCLUSION

Ultrasound is termed as one of the simplest technique used for evaluation and prediction of breast masses with three major factors they are time-saving, cost-saving and accurate results. It is advised as the first line of treatment for women suspected with issues faced related to breast. The sensitivity ratio for detection of breast masses is expected to be very high as compared to other methods being used. The evaluation is done on the basis of sonographic images of a simple cyst also eliminates the need for further invasive groups and procedures, including biopsy and aspirations. The ultimate role of ultrasound proves beneficial in the detection of carcinoma of the breast, which requires proper screening to be done of carcinoma breast.

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